

1 **TCF19 drives treatment resistance in triple negative breast cancer.**

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6 In the clinic, oncology outcomes can be classified as a pathologic complete response, pCR, meaning the
7 patient has responded to therapy, the disease (grossly) appears to have fully remitted, and the histology
8 confirms this clinical observation, a partial response or stable disease. We previously identified homeobox
9 activation - specifically, transcriptional induction of *PBX1* - in humans with HER2+ breast cancer as a
10 major mechanism by which treatment resistance operates by measuring and comparing total transcription
11 in the breast tumors of HER2+ cancer patient with pCR or a partial response (PR), an incomplete
12 response which we interpret as treatment failure (i.e., resistance). Here we measured total transcription in
13 the primary tumor in a cohort of women with triple negative breast cancer (TNBC), comparing tumor
14 transcriptomes based on presence or absence of pathologic complete response: treatment responsive or
15 treatment resistant. With this methodology we identified *TCF19* as the gene whose expression most
16 significantly correlated with treatment resistance in humans with TNBC treated with standard neoadjuvant
17 chemotherapy, across the entire transcriptome. Like *PBX1* in humans with HER2+ breast cancer, *TCF19*
18 was transcriptionally activated in the tumors of humans with TNBC who failed to achieve pCR. We then
19 measured total transcription in the normal breast and in the primary tumors of humans with triple negative
20 breast cancer, and discovered *TCF19* as a TNBC-specifying homeobox. *TCF19* is a therapeutic target for
21 humans with treatment resistant breast cancer: patients whose disease failed to respond to treatment with
22 chemotherapy. Homeoboxes drive resistance in cancer because they define the identity of the primary
23 tumor, and thus their expression controls clinical response: recurrence and resistance.
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